

FAIR 4 Research Software workshop

Morane Gruenpeter, Paula A. Martinez, Anna-Lena Lamprecht,
Carlos Martinez, Michelle Barker, Daniel S. Katz, Leyla Garcia, Neil
Chue Hong, Fotis Psomopoulos and Jennifer Harrow

Collaborative notes: <https://tinyurl.com/y6b24eyz>

Agenda

17:00	SORSE intro Goal of the workshop FAIR & FAIR software intro with live activity
18:00	Break
18:15	FAIR4RS introduction to the Working Group Update of the 4 subgroups work Questions and answers
18:50	Break
19:00- 20:00	Breakout groups 1. What does interoperability mean for software? 2. What does reusability mean for software? 3. How would you want to get credit for making your software FAIR? Report back Next steps

Workshop's goals

- Build skills in the **development of principles and standards** by contributing to the drafting of a set of FAIR principles relevant to research software
- **Understand** the fundamental properties and uses of research software
- **Build new collaborations** and engage with other RSEs and community members
- Consider how **RSEs could play a critical role** in advancing the FAIR for research software agenda, as early adopters, champions, case study contributors, and in ways that support regional/disciplinary RSE priorities

The big picture

Apollo 11 Guidance Computer (~60.000 lines), 1969

"When I first got into it, nobody knew what it was that we were doing. It was like the Wild West."

Margaret Hamilton

Tim Berners-Lee invented the **World Wide Web, 1989**, while working at CERN on a NeXT machine

“When somebody has learned how to program a computer ... **You're joining a group of people who can do incredible things. They can make the computer do anything they can imagine.**”

From *An Insight, An Idea* with Tim Berners-Lee at 27:27 (25 January 2013)

Version control systems timeline

<https://archive.softwareheritage.org/>

Research Software Engineers

“On a beautifully sunny day in **March 2012**, a small group met at Queen’s College Oxford and challenged a long-standing problem: why is there no career for software developers in academia? They didn’t know it at the time, but this meeting led to a nationwide campaign that created a vibrant and rapidly growing community, and established **a new role in research: the Research Software Engineer.**”

From the blog post by **Simon Hettrick**, Deputy Director

Posted by s.aragon on 17 August 2016 - 2:26pm

<https://www.software.ac.uk/blog/2016-08-17-not-so-brief-history-research-software-engineers-0>

The Research Software Engineer, R. Baxter, N. Chue Hong, D. Gorissen, J. Hetherington, I. Todorov, Digital Research Conference, Oxford, September, 2012

Reproducibility and academic badges

ACM take on Reproducibility, Replicability and Source code

Terminology (no consensus yet!)

- **Repeatability** \ same team, same experimental setup
- **Reproducibility*** \ different team, same experimental setup
- **Replicability*** \ different team, different experimental setup

**"As a result of discussions with the National Information Standards Organization (NISO), it was recommended that ACM harmonize its terminology and definitions with those used in the broader scientific research community"*

[NISO Taxonomy, Definitions, and Recognition Badging Scheme Working Group](#)

Where we stand?

2016 - The FAIR guiding principles ([Wilkinson et al. 2016](#))

Do software artifacts require different FAIR principles?

2018 - The **Turning FAIR into reality** report recommends that the FAIR guiding principles should be applied broadly ([European Commission, 2018](#)), which includes software source code, workflows and combination of these with specific mention in action 16.2

Action 16.2: *The FAIR data principles and this Action Plan must be tailored for specific contexts - in particular to the relevant research field - and the precise application nuanced, while respecting the objective of maximising data accessibility and reuse. Stakeholders: Research communities; Data service providers; Policymakers*

2020 - `Six Recommendations for Implementation of FAIR Practice` ([FAIR Practice TF, 2020](#)) including a full section covering the FAIR practices for digital objects that are not research data

Recommendation n°5: Recognise that FAIR guidelines will require translation for other digital objects and support such efforts.

2019 - the **Opportunity Note** by the French national Committee for Open Science's Free Software and Open Source Project Group ([Clément-Fontaine, 2019](#))

Recommendation n° 2 : Make sure the specific nature of software is recognized and not considered as “just data” particularly in the context of discussion about the notion of FAIR data.

Research Software: pillar of Open Science

FAIR doesn't necessarily mean *open*, but as stated in ([Mons et al., 2017](#)) requires clarity and transparency to **A**ccess and **R**euse conditions.

*“Based on the FAIR software metrics/indicators, communities will be able to agree on degrees of **FAIRness** that the different kinds of software should comply to, in order to reflect their Open Science ideals.”* ([Lamprecht et al., 2019](#)).

*Three pillars of Open Science
Gruenpeter, Software Heritage
CC-By 4.0 2019*

FAIR & Software

2019 - Towards FAIR principles for research software ([Lamprecht et al., 2019](#))

- published in the Data Science journal, issue 'FAIR Data, Systems and Analysis'
- translating the FAIR principles to research software.

2020 - Assessment report on 'FAIRness of software' ([Gruenpeter et al., 2020](#))

- published by the FAIRsFAIR project work package 2 task 2.4 - FAIR services & software
- analysis of nine resources that call for better recognition of software in academia
- introduce 10 high-level recommendations for future work to define FAIR principles or other requirements for research software in the scholarly domain and discuss next steps

[Join Webinar 23/11](#)

Four pillars: Archive, Reference, Describe, Credit 2020 - EOSC Scholarly Infrastructures for Research Software

[Link to document](#) waiting for the EU commission publication (community consultation ended on the 10.11.2020)

FAIR software initiatives and outcomes

“Applying FAIR Principles to Software” at the 2017 Workshop on Sustainable Software Sustainability (WOSS17)

“Making Software FAIR” at the DTL Communities@Work 2018 Conference

“FAIRness assessment for software” at the 2018 DBCLS/NBDC BioHackathon

“Sharing Your Software – What is FAIR?” at the 2018 American Geophysical Union (AGU) Fall Meeting

Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Global Sprint, including “10 easy things to make your software FAIR” 2019

“FAIR principles for Software” at 2019 Workshop on Sustainable Software Sustainability (WOSS19)

“FAIR Software” Birds of a Feather meeting at deRSE 2019

“Five recommendations for FAIR software” at NL-RSE 2019

TIB Training workshops on FAIR Data and Software 2018 - 2019

Towards FAIR principles for research software 2019 DOI: 10.3233/DS-190026

FAIR Computational Workflows 2020 DOI: 10.1162/dint_a_00033

FAIRsFAIR T2.4: assessment report on FAIRness of software

From FAIR research data toward FAIR and open research software

Lorentz Workshop 9-13 March 2020 (Automated Workflow Composition in the Life Sciences)

BRDI NAS Washington 16-17 March 2020

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/software-source-code-ig/wiki/fair4software-reading-materials>

FAIR 4 Research Software (FAIR4RS)

Main objective

Defining FAIR principles for
research software

[Join the Working Group](#)

Timeline

April 2020 - Formed after the RDA VP15

July 2020 - Launched with 4 subgroups

September 2020 - Endorsed by RDA

More details after the FAIR activity...

FAIR activity with Anna-Lena Lamprecht

FAIR 4 Research Software workshop

FAIR4RS update

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Acknowledgement

We acknowledge

- All the members and contributors of the FAIR for Research Software Working group #FAIR4RS ~140 members
- present and past steering committee members for coordinating a range of activities

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/fair-4-research-software-fair4rs-wg>

Introduction #FAIR4RS

- A joint RDA Working Group, FORCE11 Working Group, and Research Software Alliance (ReSA) Taskforce.
- Coordinating of a range of existing community-led discussions on:
 - How to define and effectively apply FAIR principles to research software,
 - How to achieve adoption of these principles.

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/fair-4-research-software-fair4rs-wg/case-statement/fair-research-software-wg-case-statement>

Motivation

- FAIR data principles strongly contribute to addressing different challenges with regard to research data
- FAIR Principles, at a high level, are intended to apply to all research objects; both those used in research and those that are research outputs
- However, the details depend on the type of research object
 - Software is not (just) data
- We focus on the adaptation and adoption of the FAIR principles to research software

FAIR4RS WG Deliverables

<p>A document developed with community support defining FAIR principles for research software</p>	<p>month 6</p>
<p>A document providing guidelines on how to apply the FAIR principles for research software (based on existing frameworks)</p>	<p>month 12</p>
<p>A document summarising the definition of the FAIR principles for research software, implementation guidelines and adoption examples</p>	<p>month 18</p>

Ice breaker

Write in the collaborative notes:

- Please add yourself to the list of participants.
- Let us know if you are registered as a participants of the FAIR4RS WG.
- And if you have participated in any activities or subgroups.

<https://tinyurl.com/y6b24eyz>

Initial phase → Subgroups work

- Aim: Pre-work to writing the principles
- Running from July – November 2020
- Subgroups
 - A fresh look at FAIR for Research Software
 - FAIR work in other contexts
 - Research software definition
 - New research related to FAIR Software

Subgroups report

<https://tinyurl.com/y6b24eyz>

Subgroup 1: A fresh look at FAIR for Research Software

Aim: examine the FAIR principles in the context of research software from scratch, not based on pre-existing work

- Group (~15 members) read original FAIR principles paper
- Voted on each foundational (F, A, I, R) principles and each guiding (15) principle
 - Applies as written; Applies with changes; Doesn't apply
- Added discussion to collaborative working document (why they voted as they did)
- Discussion summarized in new draft document on FAIR principles for research software
- Iteratively working through document, plus 2 virtual meetings (and 1 to come)
- Document is now almost complete

Subgroup 1: A fresh look at FAIR for Research Software

Draft FAIR for research software principles document

- Explain differences between data and software
- Initial translation: "(Meta)data" expands to "metadata and data", then becomes "metadata and software"
- Continued translation and discussion
 - Add new principle "Metadata about software should follow the FAIR data principles"
 - F & A: basically not changed, but gaps appear
 - I: updated principles based on focus on interoperability facilitated by the exchange of FAIR metadata or data between software, and the FAIR metadata, and data
 - R: updated principles based on focus on both use and re-use of software
- Gaps exposed: multiple aspects of software metadata and software identifiers, software complexity, documentation
- New statement of FAIR for research software principles

Next steps

- Compare and contrast with Lamprecht et al. and others as summarized in FAIRsFAIR report

Or

- Combine with other subgroup outputs, then compare and contrast with Lamprecht et al. etc.

Subgroup 2: FAIR work in other contexts

Aim: Analyse how FAIR principles are applied to research objects other than data/software:

- Computational notebooks
- Training materials
- Computational workflows (not completed)
- Other types of research objects

[Final report](#) contains potential recommendations on applying FAIR principles to encompass a range of research objects

Training materials

1. Always provide a simple download (e.g. .zip, .tar.gz) containing all course materials, so that it can be used (easily) offline
2. [Schema.org](#) usage: consider [LearningResource](#) for training material, consider if the [Course](#) could also assist (e.g., if your training materials are part of a course)

Subgroup 2: FAIR work in other contexts

Computational notebooks

1. Traceability and temporality of software and its version is an open challenge
2. Software citation is important

Research objects in general

1. PIDs key for findability but not much said about identification of versions, releases or commits, or what granularity level should be covered for software (or other research objects using some versioning)
2. Specialized registries are useful for findability narrowed by domain or community
3. Citation is important

Subgroup 3: Research software definition

Aim: review existing definitions and will specify the scope for the WG outputs

Goal measurements:

- *Specific* – concise community definition
- *Measurable* – citable and easily located
- *Assignable* – FAIR4RS-subgroup3
- *Realistic* – not sure it is :-)
- *Time-related* – ~~October 2020~~–December 2020

Status:

- collected quotes
- collected software examples to review in the examples table
- voted on the examples

Output: concise community definition of research software to provide scope for FAIR software principles

Lead: Morane Gruenpeter (Inria, Software Heritage)

Subgroup 4: New research related to FAIR Software

Aim: Review recent research and studies around FAIR software. This includes:

- Desk review to identify new papers, reports, workshops, etc.
- Summarise lessons and add relevant outputs to the [FAIR4RS Zotero Group](#)
- Re-read [Towards FAIR principles for research software](#); has state of FAIR software changed?
- Determine how these insights relate to the definition and application of FAIR principles for research software, e.g. around size/scale, practice, challenges, successful approaches, FAIR-like work

Status:

- Running [survey](#) to get feedback on rewritten FAIR principles from Towards FAIR principles paper, and gather examples of how people perceive the application of FAIR principles to software
 - Will analyse top 3-5 issues; use as basis to identify additional work that can inform these issues

Output: up-to-date identification of approaches that can help structure FAIR4RS work, in form of Zotero reading list and short report on important insights from review and survey

Lead: Neil Chue Hong

Subgroup 4: New research related to FAIR Software

Early results from the survey show:

- Respondents consider Findability and Accessibility the most important foundational principles
- There is a role for digital repositories which store many different types of research objects to help make software findable
- Clarity is required around what should be defined for accessibility around protocols
- Interoperability, even as redefined in the paper, isn't clearly defined
- Reusability needs to be better defined for software
- How to treat complex software objects needs to be considered by the principles

We need more input and feedback - take the survey:

<https://forms.gle/XLSjbybtjKZuxom39>

Questions?

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Breakout room activity

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Group work discussions

Room	Subject	facilitator
N°1	What does interoperability mean for software?	Fotis / Leyla
N°2	What does reusability mean for software?	Carlos
N°3	How would you want to get credit for making your software FAIR?	Paula / Neil

<https://tinyurl.com/y6b24eyz>

Breakout rooms

Collaborative notes: <https://tinyurl.com/y6b24eyz>

These slides

- People pick their group. Total duration 30 minutes.
- Do a round table for introductions, who is in the breakout room (5 minutes).
- The Group lead will present the question and the motivation (3 -5 minutes).
- Open discussion. Please make sure to transcribe into the table for each breakout.
- Back to the main room, to share outcomes (3 minutes each group).

Next steps

[These slides](#)

Notes: <https://tinyurl.com/y6b24eyz>

Community engagement plans

Notes: <https://tinyurl.com/y6b24eyz>

These slides

- What 2021 events would be a good location for FAIR4RS principles consultation?
- What organisations or events would like to work with us to enable consultation in your community?
- What types of materials would be helpful to facilitate discussions about FAIR 4 Research Software?

FAIR4RS Roadmap

FAIR4RS Roadmap outlines how to make FAIR research software a reality:

- Map FAIR4RS projects into a longer-term framework and guide further investment
- Identify potential collaborators/leads
- Identify opportunities for FAIR data initiatives
- Identification of Roadmap elements that are specific to research software

How to get involved

Events with FAIR4RS focus: Join [FAIR4RS group](#) to receive updates

- FAIRsFAIR webinar on [decoding the FAIR principles for software](#) - 23 November 2020
- [Collaborations Workshop](#) (CW21) 30 March - 1 April 2021

- FAIR4RS Roadmap workshop at [International FAIR Convergence Symposium](#) 1 December
- Subscribe to FAIR4RS Roadmap updates <http://eepurl.com/gY9-vv>

Thank you for joining
Thanks to our partners

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-research-software-fair4rs-wg>